

Microwave induced halodecarboxylation of α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids[†]

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Halodecarboxylations of α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids **1a-g**, **4** by *N*-chlorobenzotriazole under 5–10 minutes of microwave irradiation gave the corresponding β -arylvinyl halides **3a-g**, **5** in yields of 70–90%.

β -Arylvinyll halides are useful for the preparation of stilbenes by Heck reactions^{1,2}, arylselenoethenes³, styryl aryl sulphones⁴, β -arylvinyl thioethers⁵, 3-arylacrylonitriles⁶ and arylacetylenes⁷.

The decarboxylative halogenation of α,β -unsaturated aryl carboxylic acids to give β -arylvinyl halides has been extensively researched⁸. The Hunsdiecker reaction, emerged as a useful method of synthesis of organic halides from carboxylic acids^{9,10}: classically¹¹ it used Ag^I salts but later modifications using Hg^{II}, Tl^I and Pb^{IV} carboxylates improved yields^{8,12,13}. However, all these Hunsdiecker type reactions are of limited applicability because of temperatures, volume of solvent, reaction times, yields, and/or toxic metals^{8,12,14,15}.

A further major improvement has recently been achieved by Tokuda and coworkers who achieved the synthesis of β -arylvinyl chlorides, bromides and iodides with *N*-halosuccinimide in high yields using 1–2 minutes of microwave irradiation¹⁶. However, the by-product succinimide has to be removed by column chromatography.

We now report that *N*-chlorobenzotriazole can advantageously replace *N*-chlorosuccinimide in Tokuda's procedure to provide β -arylvinyl chlorides in high yields with the advantage that in modified procedure, pure products can be obtained in high yields without chromatographic separation because the by-product benzotriazole can be easily removed by washing with a saturated solution of aqueous Na₂CO₃.

Discussion

Cinnamic acid reacted with *N*-chlorobenzotriazole in acetonitrile and water (4 : 1) solution by irradiating at 50° for 5–10 minutes to give the maximum yield of **3a**. The reaction conditions were optimized for the synthesis of β -

arylvinylhalides by using different combinations of temperature, time and irradiation power in order to achieve the maximum yield at the lowest reaction temperature and the following combinations were used : temperatures of 40–80°; time of 5–15 min and irradiation powers of 200–300 Watts. The progress of the reaction was followed by TLC. These preliminary experiments enabled the reactions conditions to be standardized : it was concluded that irradiation of the reaction mixture at 50° for 5–10 minutes, using a power of 200 Watts was the optimum. The amount of *N*-chlorobenzotriazole and LiOAc also affected the yield and it was found that the use of equimolar amounts of the acid and *N*-chlorobenzotriazole together with a catalytic amount (4 mol %) of LiOAc gave the maximum yield with high stereoselectivity. The best results were obtained when acetonitrile and water in the ratio of 4 : 1 was used as solvent. (*E*)-3-Aryl-2-alkenoic acids gave exclusively (*E*)- β -arylvinyl halides.

These standard conditions were applied to a series of substituted cinnamic acids including the *p*-methoxy, *o*-chloro, *p*-chloro and *m*-nitro derivatives (**1b-e**). These reactions afforded products **3b-3e** in 78–87% yield (Scheme 1, Table 1). Known compounds **3b-e** were compared with literature melting points, and NMR (for oils). Elemental analysis also supported the suggested structures for **3b**, **3e** and **5**.

In addition to the ring substituted cinnamic acids, α -substituted cinnamic acid (**1f**) also (Table 1) gave the

Scheme 1. Synthesis of β -arylvinyl chlorides (**3a-g**).

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Table 1. Conditions used for the synthesis of β -arylvinyl chlorides (3a-g)

R ¹	R ²	Time (min)	Temp (°C)	Power (Watts)	Yield (%)	
3a	-C ₆ H ₅	5	50	200	75	
3b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	5	50	200	81	
3c	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	5	50	200	83	
3d	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	5	50	200	78	
3e	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	10	50	200	87	
3f	-C ₆ H ₅	-CH ₃	10	50	200	88
3g	1-Naphthyl	H	10	50	200	89

expected chloro derivative **3f** in 88% yield (characterized by elemental analysis) as a mixture of *E* and *Z* isomers in the ratio of 70/30.

The method was then applied to β -1-naphthylacrylic acid to give 1- β -chloroethylnaphthalene (**3g**) in 89% yield which was characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and elemental analysis.

This method has also been used for the synthesis of 1,4-bis-(2-chloroethenyl)benzene (**5**) from the corresponding acid.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of 1,4-bis-(2-chloroethenyl)benzene (**5**).

The advantages of microwave induction are that it is a fast reaction which involves use of little or no solvent, no use of hazardous chemicals and excludes the post reaction column chromatographic purification of the product, giving excellent yields for the synthesis of less known chloro compounds.

To summarize, this paper provides a simple method for the conversion of α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids to β -arylvinyl halides using *N*-chlorobenzotriazole as the decarboxylative chlorinating agent. The product **3** was obtained in higher yield and required a shorter reaction time.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. All the reactions under microwave irradiation were conducted in heavy-walled Pyrex tubes sealed with aluminum crimp caps fitted with a silicon septum under controlled conditions. Single mode microwave irradiation was used at a fixed temperature, pressure and irradiation power during the reaction time by an automatic power control. Microwave heating was carried out with a

single mode cavity Discover microwave synthesizer (CEM Corp., NC), producing continuous irradiation at 2455 MHz. ¹H NMR (300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (75 MHz) spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ (with TMS for ¹H and chloroform-*d* for ¹³C as the internal reference) unless specified otherwise.

1-Chloro-1*H*-benzotriazole (**2**) was synthesized according to the previously published procedure¹⁷: white crystals (94%), m.p. 104–106° (lit. m.p. 103–105°)¹⁷. *trans*-Cinnamic-acids (**1b**, **1d-e**, **1g**, **4**) were prepared by the reaction of aryl aldehydes with malonic acid in presence of pyridine and traces of piperidine as base under microwave irradiation¹⁸.

General procedure for the halodecarboxylation of α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acids (3a-g and 5) using microwave irradiation :

A dried heavy-walled Pyrex tube containing a small stirring bar was charged with α,β -unsaturated carboxylic acid (**1a-g**, **4**) (2.0 mmol), *N*-chlorobenzotriazole (**2**) (0.31 g, 2.0 mmol) and catalytic amount of lithium acetate (4% by weight) using minimum volume of acetonitrile : water (4 : 1 v/v) as solvent to make a slurry. The tube containing the reaction mixture was sealed with an aluminum crimp cap fitted with a silicon septum and then it was exposed to microwave irradiation for 5–10 minutes at a temperature of 50° (Table 1). The buildup of pressure in the closed reaction vessel was carefully monitored and was found to be typically in the range 4–15 psi. The reaction mixture was cooled below 30°. The reaction was monitored using TLC. On completion, the reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate and the organic layer was washed thoroughly with saturated solution of aqueous sodium carbonate (4 × 20 ml) and brine (2 × 20 ml) to remove formed benzotriazole. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to give pure compound. The structure of the known liquid compounds were confirmed by comparison with the NMR data available in the literature.

Z-1-(2-Chloroethenyl)benzene (**3a**)¹⁹: Yellow oil; yield 75%; ¹H NMR δ 6.63 (1H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 6.82 (1H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 7.23–7.34 (5H, m); ¹³C NMR δ 118.6, 126.1, 128.1, 128.7, 133.2, 134.8.

Z-1-(2-Chloroethenyl)phenyl methyl ether (**3b**)²⁰: Yellow oil; yield 81%; ¹H NMR δ 3.79 (3H, s), 6.48 (1H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 13.7 Hz), 6.82–6.85 (2H, m), 7.19–7.22 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR δ 55.2, 114.1, 116.3, 127.3, 127.6, 132.6, 159.5 (Found : C, 64.06; H, 5.44; N, 0.40. Calcd. for C₉H₉ClO : C, 64.11; H, 5.44; N, 0.0%).

Z-1-Chloro-2-(2-chloroethenyl)benzene (**3c**)²¹: Yellow oil; yield 83%; ¹H NMR δ 6.67 (1H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 7.19–

7.26 (3H, m), 7.36–7.43 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR δ 121.2, 126.8, 127.0, 129.2, 129.9, 132.6, 133.1.

Z-1-Chloro-4-(2-chloroethenyl)benzene (**3d**)²² : White solid; yield 89%; m.p. 34.5–35° (lit. 35–36°)²²; ^1H NMR δ 6.62 (1H, d, *J* 13.7 Hz), 6.77 (1H, d, *J* 13.7 Hz), 7.20–7.30 (4H, m); ^{13}C NMR δ 119.3, 127.3, 129.0, 132.1, 133.3, 133.9.

Z-1-(2-Chloroethenyl)-3-nitrobenzene (**3e**)²¹ : Yellow solid; yield 87%; m.p. 84–86° (lit. 80–82°)²¹; ^1H NMR δ 6.81 (1H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 6.89 (1H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 7.49–7.54 (1H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.61 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 8.10–8.15 (2H, m); ^{13}C NMR δ 120.7, 122.2, 122.7, 129.8, 131.2, 131.9, 136.5, 148.6 (Found : C, 52.30; H, 3.13; N, 7.53. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{ClNO}_2$: C, 52.34; H, 3.29; N, 7.63%).

I-(2-Chloro-1-propenyl)benzene (**3f**)²³ : (mixture of isomers) Yellow oil; yield 88%; ^1H NMR δ 2.25 (1H, s), 6.70 (1H, s), 7.17–7.34 (4H, m), 7.55 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz); ^{13}C NMR δ (as appears in spectrum) 22.4, 127.1, 128.0, 128.4, 132.9, 135.9.

I-(2-Chloroethenyl)naphthalene (**3g**)²⁴ : Yellow oil; yield 89%; ^1H NMR δ 6.56 (1H, d, *J* 13.3 Hz), 7.33–7.52 (5H, m), 7.74–7.81 (2H, m), 7.94–7.98 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR δ 120.5, 123.7, 124.1, 125.5, 126.0, 126.4, 128.5, 128.6, 130.7, 131.0, 132.3, 133.5.

1,4-Bis-(2-chloroethenyl)benzene (**5**) : White crystals; yield 79%; m.p. 70–72°; ^1H NMR δ 6.71 (2H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz), 6.86 (2H, d, *J* 13.7 Hz), 7.31 (4H, s); ^{13}C NMR δ 119.1, 126.5, 132.7, 134.6 (Found : C, 60.10; H, 3.93; N, 0.0. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{ClNO}_2$: C, 60.33; H, 4.05; N, 0.0%).

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